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Factors Affecting the Literacy Development of Students from the Roma/Travelling Community

A Review of the Research

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A summary highlighting key conclusions and findings

The key findings surrounding supporting literacy and numeracy development of Roma and Traveller learners across the curriculum include:

- limited research was found on this topic, future research specific to literacy and numeracy development should be explored
- awareness and access to early years education should be promoted to reinforce literacy and numeracy skill development (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020)
- language awareness and support of Roma and Traveller bilingual students should be provided in schools (Aguiar et al., 2019; Heltai, 2020).
- cultural awareness and intercultural education should be fostered in the classroom (Kennedy & Smith, 2019; Salgado et. al, 2019)
- the role of Roma and Traveller mediators should be explored in the Irish context, e.g. in the role of teaching assistants (Salgado-Orellana, de Luna a& Sánchez-Núñez, 2019)
- initial teacher training and continuous professional development should be provided to teachers to develop cultural awareness of the Roma and Traveller communities and instruct teachers of approaches to supported Roma and Traveller students (Salgado et. al, 2019)
- supporting Roma and Traveller caregivers in accessing resources for education (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Kennedy & Smith, 2019)
- *Supporting Families* through parental involvement, especially in the early years, is essential for promoting the development of Roma and Traveller children's language and literacy e.g. family literacy programmes (Rose, 2013)
- supporting families and students transition from primary to secondary level (Department of Justice and Equality, 2017)

Recommendations

- **Enabling parents and communities**
 - *Further research into education initiatives and supports for members of the Roma and travelling community* on the implementation of interventions on a larger scale, which would provide clearer information for improving student education in the future, particularly in relation to specific literacy and numeracy interventions e.g. through NEPs action research projects. Then these results could be analysed and meta-analyses carried out to determine a more in-depth analysis of effect sizes.
 - *Promoting access to early childhood education* will inform families of the educational benefits of this programme. Access to this programme could be promoted by community liaisons, taking into account the nomadic culture of some members of the Roma and Irish travelling community, which may result in a need to connect families with early childhood education providers in different localities (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020).
 - *Access to resources* should be supported for students with socioeconomic disadvantage, and this support needs to follow families as they move from one location to the next (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Kennedy & Smith, 2019).
 - *Mediators in Education*, such as teaching assistants, should be appointed to work collaboratively with teachers, parents and students. The ‘teaching assistant’ preferably should be a member of the Roma or travelling to promote belonging and connection between the child and the school. The work of mentors can be beneficial in addressing language and communication difficulties that may present (Salgado-Orellana, de Luna a& Sánchez-Núñez, 2019).
 - *Supporting Families* through parental involvement, especially in the early years and transition to second level, is essential for promoting the development of Roma and Traveller children’s language and literacy e.g. family literacy programmes (Rose, 2013).
 - Best ways to support transitions to second level should be explored in an Irish context (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2016, cited in Kennedy & Smith, 2019)
- **Teachers and ECEC CPD**

- *Language Support* for students and parents is essential in ensuring education is accessible for members of the Roma and Travelling communities. Recognition and support of the bilingual/multilingual abilities of these students can be expected to impact children's achievement (Aguiar et al., 2019; Heltai, 2020).
- *Initial teacher education and professional development* should educate and inform teachers of the unique cultural values of Roma and Irish Travellers, and how best to support children from these groups in an inclusive classroom. Professional development should be ongoing for practising teachers (Salgado et. al, 2019).
- **Curriculum and the learning experience**
 - *Cultural awareness and education. The curriculum should include aspects of Roma history and culture.* Educators should implement 'intercultural education policies' to ensure Roma and Irish Traveller cultures are represented well and respected in the school environment and curriculum (Kennedy & Smith, 2019; Salgado et. al, 2019).

Overview

The umbrella-term 'Roma' encompasses diverse groups, including Roma, Sinti, Kale, Romanichels, Boyash/Rudari, Ashkali, Egyptians, Yenish, Dom, Lom, Rom and Abdal, as well as Traveller populations (gens du voyage, Gypsies, Camminanti, etc.) The Roma are Europe's largest ethnic minority. Out of an estimated 10 to 12 million Roma living in Europe, approximately 6 million are citizens or residents of the EU (European Commission, 2021). In Ireland, "Travellers and Roma are among the most disadvantaged and marginalised people" (Department of Justice and Equality, 2017, p.3). Although there have been numerous developments in the area of Roma education, particularly by reducing early school-leaving and improving participation in early childhood education and compulsory schooling, the new strategic framework for the equality, inclusion and participation of Roma in EU countries and preparation of the post-2020 initiative (2020-2030) states that the cases of segregation of Roma pupils in education have increased and many EU Roma are still victims of prejudice and social exclusion, despite the discrimination ban across EU Member States including Ireland (for e.g. see Michael, 2021).

Literacy has been considered as an essential requirement for social integration and participation in modern societies. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the ability to read and write provides "[...] a solid foundation for poverty reduction and sustainable development in pursuit of a democratic and stable society" (p.4). According to European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (2016), however, on average 20% of Roma respondents reported that they could neither read nor write in stark contrast to 1% of non-Roma respondents in all EU member states (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014). These differences between Roma and non-Roma are statistically significant in all Member States.

For these reasons, the strategic framework for the equality, inclusion and participation of Roma in EU countries and preparation of the post-2020 initiative (2020-2030) recommends that all member states cut gap in participation in early childhood education and care by at least half; to ensure that by 2030 at least 70% of Roma children participate in pre-school; reduce the gap in upper secondary completion by at least one third; to ensure that by 2030 the majority of Roma

youth complete at least upper secondary education; work towards eliminating segregation by cutting at least in half the proportion of Roma children attending segregated primary schools to ensure that by 2030 less than one in five Roma child attend schools where most or all children are Roma (European Commission, 2020, p.11). Further actions are outlined in the National Traveller and Roma Inclusion Strategy 2017-2021 (Department of Justice and Equality, 2017), including facilitation in the provision of free pre-school places, promoting parental engagement in education and supporting Traveller and Roma attendance and engagement with the education system at primary and post primary levels. This systematic literature review identifies and synthesises the relevant literature in the area of Roma literacy and numeracy practices in the European context post-2011. It analyses elements that affect literacy and numeracy development and how learning can be supported for Roma children.

Research Question

The study seeks to identify and analyse existing evidence related to Roma children literacy and numeracy development. It intends to identify key recommendations for progressing the quality inclusive mainstream education specifically in the area of development of Roma literacy and numeracy skills and to provide insights into ways in which NCCA can continue to support equal access to and inclusion of Roma children within mainstream education. The research was underpinned by the following questions:

1. What factors affect the learning of students from the Roma/Travelling community?
2. How can learners from Roma/Travelling community be supported in developing literacy and numeracy skills within/ across the curriculum?

Key Search Terms

Systematic searches were carried out on online databases the Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), EBSCO, Google Scholar and The following terms were in the data search. "Roma" OR "Romani" OR "Roma people" OR "Traveller" OR "travelling community" AND "literacy" OR "writing" OR "reading" OR "education" or "digital literacy" OR "numeracy" OR "maths" OR "math" AND ("meta-analysis" OR "systematic review").

Exclusion criteria

All studies dated before 2011 were excluded, as well as texts not available in English. Although meta-analyses and systematic reviews were prioritized, literature reviews and grey literature, including relevant single case studies were included. The number of participants involved in studies across the research was notably small. Very little emerged from the search in terms of literacy and numeracy. No literature was found relevant to digital literacy. Research based on the early years, primary and secondary levels were included, although more research exists related to adult education. The PRISMA ¹chart below documents the systematic search process.

¹ *Template From:* Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71 For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

1. Prisma 2020 diagram

Overview of results

A limited number of (6) studies were found during data searches. Notably, there is a scarcity of meta-analysis or systematic reviews concerning the childhood education of children from the Roma and Travelling community. One systematic review (of 17 articles) emerged from the search (Salgado-Orellana, de Luna & Sánchez-Núñez, 2019). This review focuses on intercultural education as an educational intervention targeting Roma students. Two extensive literature reviews were also included, one of which focused on 78 early interventions tackling inequalities experienced by Roma children in 8 European countries (Aguiar, Silva, Guerra, Rodrigues, Ribeiro, Pastori, Leseman & the ISOTIS research team, 2020) and the other an examination of two decades of research (151 articles) on Roma and education in Europe (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018). Two smaller-scale empirical studies were also included as they provide valuable insights not addressed by meta-analytic literature - implementing a translanguaging approach with 22 bilingual students (Heltai, 2020), and insight into family literacy programmes (with 30 participants) in an Irish context (Rose, 2013). One piece of grey literature (involving 108 Roma parents) was also included (Kennedy & Smith, 2019), as its findings relate to wider factors that affect the education of Roma children in Ireland. The included studies are largely situated in European contexts. There is limited information on supporting children at the second level. No literature in English was found meeting the criteria which focus specifically on digital literacy or maths/numeracy. For further detail of reviewed studies, see Appendix X 1 Tabulation.

Synthesis of systematic literature review findings

Several themes emerged from the literature review, including early years education, language recognition and support, cultural awareness and education, access to resources, mediators in education, teacher education, supporting families and second level education.

Early Years Education and Roma children

A growing body of research highlights early childhood education as an opportunity to support the educational achievement of learners from the Roma and travelling communities (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020). Providing access to early education promotes the inclusion

of minority groups such as Roma and traveller children in the education system (OECD 2015, 2016, as cited in Aguiar et al., 2020). An increased resource allocation to early childhood education, particularly for members of the Travelling and Roma communities, is highlighted in the implementation of the EU Child Guarantee (European Commission, 2019) and underpins the EU's First Years First Priority campaign (European Commission, 2022). However, education for children is not mandatory until age six/seven in many EU countries. Kennedy & Smith's (2019) article examining data collected from the first Irish national needs assessment of Roma indicated that 40% of children under the age of 5 from Roma households were attending pre-school (which begins at age 3 in Ireland). Absenteeism, largely caused by a lack of promotion of social inclusion by education systems, was highlighted in Lauritzen & Nodeland's (2018) literature review of research on Roma and education in Europe. The researchers emphasise the significance of early childhood education (Horvoi, 2010) in response to reports of educational underachievement experienced among Romani students (p.158). In Aguir et. al.'s (2020) literature review of early interventions tackling inequalities experienced by immigrant, low-income, and Roma children in Europe, only 20% of interventions were reported to take place at pre-primary school age level. The majority of the interventions at this age occurred within the ECE classroom setting, and involved teachers, engaging with families and providing language support for students. ECE settings can provide naturalistic and comprehensive interventions, which can "result in increased sustainability and potentiate the positive effects of ECEC on children's future learning and adjustment" (Melhuish et al. 2015, as cited in Aguir et. al., 2020, p.69). Aguir et al. further argue that early childhood education in and of itself could be considered an educational intervention. Providing access to school, including early childhood education, can prove difficult for nomadic ethnic groups in Europe (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights 2016; Gkofa 2017), and efforts should be made to further facilitate access to early childhood education for Roma children and children from the travelling community. Comprehensive anti-bias training for ECE educators should be implemented (Murray, 2012; Department for Children, Equality, Diversity, Inclusion and Youth, 2021). Kennedy & Smith (2019) found that family support workers were confident that there would be value in working alongside Roma advocates to inform and educate parents

regarding free access to early years education, as well as the benefits of developmentally appropriate learning through play, which occurs in this setting.

Language Recognition and Support

Language is a key element of the Roma and Travelling community cultures. According to the European Commission's (2019) analysis of education systems in Europe, the home language of a student from the Roma/ Travelling community is usually not the primary language used to communicate at school, and it is seldom supported in the school environment. There is a "prevalent monolingual paradigm in most European publicly funded schools" (Busch, 2011, cited in Aguiar et al., 2019, p.60), even though many Roma/traveller children and their parents may not be proficient in mainstream languages. Gkofa (2017) recommends that to aid children in overcoming cultural inequalities, greater support should be given to bilingual Roma students. Kennedy and Smith, (2019), in analysing the results of the first national needs assessment of Roma in Ireland (Pavee Point Traveller and Roma Centre and Department of Justice and Equality, 2018), found that 32% of Roma adults rely on their children to translate as interpreters, which affects children's school attendance. Aguiar et. al.'s (2019) review of 78 interventions tackling inequality experienced by Roma children, found that only a third of interventions supported or acknowledged home language. Berry's (1984, 2013) research acknowledges that support for maintaining and developing home cultures and languages is a key characteristic of multicultural policies. For example, translanguaging is an approach that showed promising results in an ongoing intervention project 'Translanguaging Classroom Communication and Effective Organisation of Learning in Tiszavasvári' in Hungary (Heltai, 2020). So far the results suggest that a translanguaging approach allows students to use their local Romani non-standardised language practices such as grassroots literacy practices occurring naturally within their communities, resulting in an improvement of their general literacy skills (p.463). The translanguaging pedagogy used in the school makes it possible for ways of speaking and literacy practices formerly deemed unsuitable for learning purposes to be integrated into school work (p.481). In this way, translanguaging pedagogy helps to acknowledge the value of different language resources in the classroom, thus promoting social justice (García and Leiva, 2014, p. 214) and offering educational

advantages. The potential of such an approach should be researched on a larger scale in an Irish context.

Cultural Awareness and Education

Findings from Lauritzen and Nodeland's (2018) review of research on Roma education in Europe highlights the influence of cultural practices and values on education and learning. Cultural dissonance, contrasting practices and expectations, and the clash of traditional value systems were reported as affecting a number of the interventions undertaken amongst Roma students. Early school leaving may be attributed to "culturally constructed perceptions of childhood and a person's life cycle" (Kiprianos et al., 2012, p. 675) and an academic learning focus can clash with Roma culture (Bedmar & León, 2012). An acknowledgement of the learning that occurs at home for Roma children, although qualitatively measured and often pedagogically different from school learning, should be noted (O'Hanlon, 2010, p. 239). Lauritzen and Nodeland (2018) further note an emerging debate regarding whether a conflict between Roma culture and education exists. Orçan, Çiçekler, and Arı's (2014) research found that Romani mothers, in particular, aspired for their children to be educated but recognised the Romani culture may at times act as a barrier. The invisibility of Roma culture in educational settings emerged as a further theme in Lauritzen and Nodeland's (2018) research. A lack of awareness of the characteristics of Roma and Irish Travellers can lead to misunderstanding and stereotyping, resulting in one-size-fits-all approaches to education. Additionally, a lack of representation of these groups in curricula creates an alienating school culture (p.163). A need for the inclusion of Roma history and culture in the Irish school curriculum was also raised in the results of the first national needs assessment of Roma in Ireland (Pavee Point Traveller and Roma Centre and Department of Justice and Equality, 2018) by both parents and service providers (Kennedy & Smith, 2019). In international policy, actions were undertaken to recognise the unique cultural influence of this community, including the Decade of Roma Inclusion policy 2005-2015. The EU Framework for National Roma Integration Strategies has resulted in member states taking steps to improve education access. Many European countries are initiating education policy reforms, including "greater recognition of Romani language and culture within school curricula" (Kennedy & Smith, 2019, p.2937). Intercultural education is a perspective that embodies citizenship and equality while recognizing

the differences and values of other cultures (Salgado Orellano et al., 2020). The adoption of such practices in an Irish context could be achieved by greater use of intercultural education. Intercultural education is recommended as part of the primary school curriculum, but there is a lack of information on the extent to which such guidelines are implemented, or whether or not the focus on the Roma/ Irish traveller culture is sufficiently strong. At second level, an active approach to the engagement and implementation of intercultural education is needed (McGinley & Keanes, 2022).

Mediators in Education

The employment of “Roma mediators” to liaise with Roma communities, families and schools (Ram 2015) has been implemented as part of policy change in many European countries (Kennedy & Smith, 2019). Providing not only language but cultural support, the use of mediators could be further explored in an Irish context. Salgado-Orellana, de Luna and Sánchez-Núñez’s (2019) systematic review of interventions and programmes that value the cultural diversity of the Roma people highlighted characteristics of inclusive practices, including teacher assistants and intercultural mediators from the Roma community. This was established to aid student and family participation. They examined a project (Zake, 2010) in Latvia undertaken at pre-school and primary level implementing intercultural education focusing on inclusive practices. “The Roma Teaching Assistant Program” took place across nine schools where educators were provided with educational information and resources regarding the history, culture, language and traditions of the Roma people. Support centres were also established where teaching assistants, who identified as part of the Roma community, worked collaboratively with teachers and parents. Salgado-Orellana et al. (2019) highlight the positive benefits of this intervention, noting that “results showed a better adaptation to school while improving their social skills, a general satisfaction from the families for seeing their ethnic necessities considered, and finally this inclusive model meets sustainability for intercultural education” (p.7). The replication of this study could be further considered within an Irish context. Salgado (2019) reinforces the importance that the “teaching assistant” is a member of the Roma or travelling community and not from the cultural majority, to promote belonging and connection between the child and the school.

Teacher Education

In the form of initial teacher training and continuous professional development, teacher education was highlighted in much of the literature synthesised. Concerning the impact of intercultural education, Salgado et. al (2019) cited this as a key recommendation amongst the interventions put forth, as “contexts need a constant update, cooperation across the curriculum and intercultural competence to develop strategies and methodologies appropriate to the cultural characteristics of this group” (p.12). Aguiar et. al’s (2020) analysis of interventions to reduce educational inequality noted that the majority of interventions occurred as part of whole-class instruction facilitated by the classroom teacher, which is consistent with recommended practices of interventions in the early years (McWilliam, 2010). Supporting the ongoing training of teachers is crucial to reducing inequalities experienced by children at disadvantage (Slot, Halba, & Romijn, 2017). Ongoing professional development is necessary to ensure teachers can lead interventions effectively (Ülger et al. 2018).

Cutting the gap – supporting Roma families

The effect of socioeconomic status on school achievement emerged as a concern in Lauritzen and Nodeland’s (2018) review of research on Roma and education in Europe. They noted that test score gaps in reading and mathematics between Roma and non-Roma pupils in Hungary can be attributed to differences in parental socio-economic status, rather than ethnicity (Kertesi & Kézdi, 2016). Ensuring parents can meet the costs of education is an important undertaking. Interestingly, Kennedy & Smith (2019) noted that nationality/residency status is not included in official Irish poverty data, but that the Habitual Residence Condition (HRC) in place in Ireland since 2004 limits access to social protection, resulting in many Roma families being unable to access financial supports e.g. the universal child benefit payment, the back-to-school clothing and footwear scheme etc. (p.2940). Uniform, book and material costs associated with education in Ireland remain high (Barnardos Ireland, 2016).

The potential of supporting family involvement in education arose across the research. Aguiar et. al (2019) identified that family involvement activities played a role in many interventions,

primarily at the early years level. These interventions focused on activities that promoted home-school communication and learning in the home (Epstein, 2011). Supporting this two-way communication between Roma and Irish traveller families and schools is essential, through the use of advocates, interpreters and community outreach workers (Kennedy & Smith, 2019). This ensures that teachers are not working under assumptions and have a greater awareness of the obstacles faced by Roma and Irish Traveller students.

An Irish case study (Rose, 2013) that focused on building on existing informal learning in Traveller communities through family literacy programmes could be researched and explored further. In this study, parents were supported by a practitioner as well as a community liaison worker during weekly workshops. The workshops provided parents with an opportunity to discuss and ask questions to the facilitator regarding their children's academic skill development and achievement. Replication of this intervention study surrounding family literacy programmes could provide valuable insight into how parents and education facilitators can improve literacy skills collaboratively.

Second Level

A limited number of articles in our search included interventions at the second level. Data from Kennedy & Smith indicates that 72% of secondary school-age children in Ireland are attending school (2019). Notably, across European countries, high rates of Roma aged 16-24 are not engaged in education, training programmes or employed (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2016, cited in Kennedy & Smith, 2019). Member countries of the European Union have committed to implementing strategies to increase school attendance and engagement at the third level (Comisión Europea, 2017). Early school leaving may be attributed to various factors, including "culturally constructed perceptions of childhood and a person's life cycle" (Kiprianos et al., 2012, p. 675). Trentini (2014) found that Roma children have lower levels of educational returns than their non-Roma peers, which may be demotivating for students. Myers et al. (2010) maintain that fears of cultural loss can affect the transition of students from primary to the second level.

Conclusion

As the FRA survey documents children and adults from Roma communities continue to navigate and negotiate layers of stereotyping and discrimination in their daily lives, and in their interactions with others in the European societies. This experience has a direct impact on their participation in education. This chapter set out the nature of the research and evidence identified through the systematic literature review. The systematic literature review searches revealed that there is limited systematic research/reviews available on the theme of Roma/ Travel literacy/numeracy development/best practices. The synthesis of existing evidence suggests that awareness and access to early years education should be promoted to reinforce literacy and numeracy skill development among Roma communities (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Aguiar et al., 2020). Supporting families through parental involvement, e.g., through family literacy programmes especially in the early years, has been considered essential for promoting the development of Roma and Traveller children's language and literacy (Rose, 2013; Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Kennedy & Smith, 2019). Some studies pointed to cultural challenges like the struggle of preservation of the unique ethnic Roma identity connected to the lack of representation, racism and segregation, socioeconomic gaps existing in the education system. The studies identify the relevance of language awareness and support of Roma and Traveller bilingual students in schools/educational settings; also pointing to the importance of cultural awareness and potential of intercultural education framework (embedded within human rights perspective) to foster literacy practices in the classroom (Aguiar et al., 2019; Heltai, 2020; Kennedy & Smith, 2019; Salgado et. al, 2019). The role of Roma and Traveller mediators has also been explored, specifically, the role of teaching assistants/mediators that are also members of the Roma community and the positive impact they have on Teacher-Parent/Student relationships (Lauritzen & Nodeland, 2018; Kennedy & Smith, 2019). Moreover, initial teacher training and continuous professional development should be provided to teachers to develop cultural awareness of the Roma and Traveller communities and instruct teachers of approaches to support Roma and Traveller students, particularly, facilitating Roma and Traveller caregivers in accessing resources for education (Salgado et. al, 2019). Finally, making sure Roma and Irish

Traveller cultures are represented well and respected in the school environment and curriculum has also been articulated (Kennedy & Smith, 2019; Salgado et. al, 2019).

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Appendix X Tabulation of Results

Review	Number of Studies	Age range	Effect Size	Finding
Aguiar, Silva, Guerra, Rodrigues, Ribeiro, Pastori, Leseman & the ISOTIS research team (2020)	78 studies in 8 European countries	Early Childhood Education and Primary Years	Not specified	An analysis of classroom and school interventions for equality for Roma children. Language support interventions by 79% of the interventions, although 22% of the interventions children's heritage language. 22% of the interventions implemented at the EDEC level and 22% of the interventions support and family involvement activities.
Heltai (2020)	22 pupil study	1 st grade, 3 rd grade and 5th-grade pupils	Not specified	A report of an ongoing project in which school educators are seeking to eliminate disadvantages for Roma students. Results indicate how translanguaging could be used in the classroom to further the learning of Roma pupils. Children develop skills that are transferrable across home and school contexts. Education and support would be recommended to implement this practice.
Kennedy & Smith (2019)	108 respondent study	Survey of parents with school-age children	Not specified	This article draws on data obtained from a national needs assessment of Roma children. Factors that affect the education of Roma children. Findings suggest that Roma children are disadvantaged and parents experience low language and literacy levels, lack of resources, and limited Roma cultural understanding.

Lauritzen & Nodeland (2018)	Literature review of 151 articles	Early years/school-age children	Not specified	A literature review provides an overview and education. The findings identify representations across the articles, including school, academic achievement, social cultural differences, invisibility, teacher hostility, segregation and misguided policies.
Rose (2013)	30 interviews with education professionals, past pupils and current pupils	Individuals accessing a family literacy programme	Not specified	An article examining the potential programmes can support student learning that family literacy programmes opportunity to develop skills to support learning at home.
Salgado-Orellana, de Luna, Sánchez-Núñez (2019)	A systematic review of 17 articles	Primary and secondary level	Not specified	A systematic review of interventions and value the cultural diversity of the Roma characteristics of inclusive practices assistants and/or intercultural mediators community to aid students, as well participation.

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